

International Journal of Advances in Engineering & Scientific Research (IJAESR)

ISSN: 2349 –3607 (Online) , ISSN: 2349 –4824 (Print)

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COMPARATIVE STUDY ON DOCUMENT TYPE DEFINITION AND XML SCHEMA DEFINITION

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Abstract

XML was designed to transport and store data, with focus on what data is. DTD is A Document Type Definition (DTD) defines the legal building blocks of an XML document. It defines the document structure with a list of legal elements and attributes. What XML Schema do is provide an Object Oriented approach to defining the format of an XML document. XML Schema provide a set of basic types.

This paper compares the XML Document Type Definition and XML Schema.

Key words: XML Document, DTD, HTML

I. Introduction

XML stands for eXtensible Markup Language. XML was designed to describe data. XML is a markup language much like HTML. XML was designed to carry data, not to display data. XML was created to structure, store, and transport information.

Example:

```
<student>
<sid>1</sid>
<sname>Rashmi</sid>
<course>BCA</course>
</student>
```

II. DTD

A Document Type Definition (DTD) defines the legal building blocks of an XML document [1]. It defines the document structure with a list of legal elements and attributes.

When an XML document is validated against a DTD by it validating XML parser. The XML, documents will he checked to ensure that all required elements are present and that no undeclared elements have been added.

An extra advantage of using DTDs in this situation is that a single DTD could be referenced by all the organization's applications [3]. .NET Framework provides a property that allows prohibiting or skipping DTD parsing [2].

There are two ways of DTD Declaration

1. Internal DTD Declaration
2. External DTD Declaration

Internal DTD Declaration

```
<?xml version="1.0"?>
<!DOCTYPE message [ <!ELEMENT message (#PCDATA)>]
<message>
Let the good times roll!
</message>
```

The internal DTD is contained within the Document type Declaration, which begins with <!DOCTYPE and ends with >. The Document Type Declaration will appear between the XML declaration and the start of the document itself (the document or root element) and identify that section of the XML document as containing a Document Type Definition. Following the Document Type Declaration (DOCTYPE), the root element of the XML document is defined (in this case, message). The DTD tells us that this document will have a single element, message that will contain parsed character data (#PCDATA).

External DTD Declaration

```
<?xml version="1.0"?>
<!DOCTYPE message SYSTEM "message.dtd" >

<message>
Let the good times roll!
</message>
```

The URL could have been used to define the location of the DTD.

Document Not valid according to defined DTD

```
<?xml version="1.0"?>
<!DOCTYPE message SYSTEM "message.dtd" >

<message>
<text>
Let the good times roll!
</text>
</message>
```

Because message.dtd does not define an element name text.

Why use DTD?

- Each of your XML files can carry a description of its own format.
- Independent groups of people can agree to use a standard DTD for interchanging data.
- Your application can use a standard DTD to verify that the data you receive from the outside world is valid.
- You can also use a DTD to verify your own data.

III. XSD

XML Schema describes the structure of an XML document. XML Schema is an XML-based alternative to DTD [4]. The XML Schema language is also referred to as XML Schema Definition (XSD).

- An XML Schema:
 - ✓ defines elements that can appear in a document
 - ✓ defines attributes that can appear in a document
 - ✓ defines which elements are child elements
 - ✓ defines the order of child elements
 - ✓ defines the number of child elements
 - ✓ defines whether an element is empty or can include text
 - ✓ defines data types for elements and attributes
 - ✓ defines default and fixed values for elements and attributes

Why use XML schema?

- XML Schemas Support Data Types
- XML Schemas use XML Syntax
- XML Schemas Secure Data Communication
- Well-Formed is not Enough

IV. Comparison Between Document Type Definition and XML Schema

	DTD (Document Type Definition)	XSD (XML Schema Definition)
Syntax	DTDs have a unique syntax held over from SGML DTD	XML Schema utilize an XML-based syntax
Data Format	DTD are derived from SGML syntax.	XML schema are written in XML
Data Type	DTD doesn't support datatypes	XML schema defines datatypes for elements and attributes
Namespace	DTD doesn't support.	XML schemas allows support for namespaces
Language	Working with DTD, user learn new language	Using XML schema user need not to learn a new language
Data communication	DTD data can be misunderstood by the receiver.	XML schema provides secure data communication i.e sender can describe the data in a way that receiver will understood.
Extensible	DTD is not extensible	XML schemas are extensible
Markup validation	Can specify only the root element in the instance document.	Any global element can be root. No ambiguous content support
Inline definition	DTD allow inline definition	XSD does not allow inline definition

Conclusion

XSD is an XML schema language recommended through W3C; DTD is a set of markup declarations used to define a document type. XSD is used to express a set of rules to which an XML document must adhere; a Document Type Definition associates a DTD with an XML document.

References

[1] <http://www.w3schools.com/DTD>

[2] Bryan Sullivan (November 2009). "[XML Denial of Service Attacks and Defenses](#)". MSDN Magazine. Retrieved 2013-10-21.

[3] Heather Williamson, "The Complete Reference XML", Tata McGraw Hill Education Private Limited

[4] Schmelzer, "XML and Web Services" Pearson